

What is a good bug report template?

Our team is investigating how to help developers create high-quality bug report templates. In literature, many tools have been proposed to automatically improve the quality of bug reports. However, there is little research on the impact of the template on the process and results of reporting bugs.

Therefore, we want to explore in-depth how templates affect projects' bug reports and what guidelines help developers flexible and effective design templates. We also expect our study could give developers diverse examples of good and bad templates to improve their own bug report templates.

From our observation of the bug report template your project adopt, you have made modifications to default templates in the GitHub community, and we deem you have a deep understanding of bug report templates. We would much appreciate it if you could answer the following eleven questions that should not take more than five minutes. (Please note all the answers will be kept anonymous and only for research purposes):

*必填

1. Q1: How many years have you used GitHub? *

(Mark only one option)

请仅选择一个答案。

- < 1 year
- 1-5 years
- 5-10 years
- > 10 years

2. Q2: What best describes the primary type of project you currently work on? *

(Mark only one option)

请仅选择一个答案。

- Database
- Framework
- Plugin
- Toolkit
- Library
- Platform
- Other

3。 Q3. What is your primary programming language you currently used *

(Mark only one option)

请仅选择一个答案。

- C/C++
- C#
- Go
- Java
- JavaScript
- Kotlin
- Objective-C
- Perl
- PHP
- Python
- R
- Ruby
- Rust
- Scala
- SQL
- Swift
- TypeScript
- Visual Basic
- 其他: _____

4. Q4: What is your country/area of residence *

请仅选择一个答案。

- Afghanistan (AFG)
- Albania (ALB)
- Algeria (DZA)
- American Samoa (ASM)
- Andorra (AND)
- Angola (AGO)
- Anguilla (AIA)
- Antigua and Barbuda (ATG)
- Argentina (ARG)
- Armenia (ARM)
- Aruba (ABW)
- Australia (AUS)
- Austria (AUT)
- Azerbaijan (AZE)
- Bahamas, The (BHM)
- Bahrain (BHR)
- Bangladesh (BGD)
- Barbados (BRB)
- Belarus (BLR)
- Belgium (BEL)
- Belize (BLZ)
- Benin (BEN)
- Bermuda (BMU)
- Bhutan (BTN)
- Bolivia (BOL)
- Bosnia and Herzegovina
- Botswana
- Brazil
- British Virgin Islands
- Brunei (BRN)
- Bulgaria (BGR)
- Burkina Faso (BFA)

- Burma (MMR)
- Burundi (BDI)
- Cabo Verde (CPV)
- Cambodia (KHM)
- Cameroon (CMR)
- Canada (CAN)
- Cayman Islands (CYM)
- Central African Republic (CAF)
- Chad (TCD)
- Chile (CHL)
- China (CHN)
- Colombia (COL)
- Comoros (COM)
- Congo, Democratic Republic of the (COD)
- Congo, Republic of the (COG)
- Cook Islands (COK)
- Costa Rica (CRI)
- Cote d'Ivoire (CIV)
- Croatia (HRV)
- Cuba (CUB)
- Curacao (CUW)
- Cyprus (CYP)
- Czech Republic (CZE)
- Denmark (DNK)
- Djibouti (DJI)
- Dominica (DMA)
- Dominican Republic (DOM)
- Ecuador (ECU)
- Egypt (EGY)
- El Salvador (SLV)
- Equatorial Guinea (GNQ)
- Eritrea (ERI)
- Estonia (EST)
- Ethiopia (ETH)
- Falkland Islands (Islas Malvinas) (FLK)Faroe Islands (FRO)

- Fiji (FJI)
- Finland (FIN)
- France (FRA)
- French Polynesia (PYF)
- Gabon (GAB)
- Gambia, The (GMB)
- Georgia (GEO)
- Germany (DEU)
- Ghana (GHA)
- Gibraltar (GIB)
- Greece (GRC)
- Greenland (GRL)
- Grenada (GRD)
- Guam (GUM)
- Guatemala (GTM)
- Guernsey (GGY)
- Guinea-Bissau (GNB)
- Guinea (GIN)
- Guyana (GUY)
- Haiti (HTI)
- Honduras (HND)
- Hong Kong (HKG)
- Hungary (HUN)
- Iceland (ISL)
- India (IND)
- Indonesia (IDN)
- Iran (IRN)
- Iraq (IRQ)
- Ireland (IRL)
- Isle of Man (IMN)
- Israel (ISR)
- Italy (ITA)
- Jamaica (JAM)
- Japan (JPN)
- Jersey (JEY)

- Jordan (JOR)
- Kazakhstan (KAZ)
- Kenya (KEN)
- Kiribati (KIR)
- Korea, North (PRK)
- Korea, South (KOR)
- Kosovo (KSV)
- Kuwait (KWT)
- Kyrgyzstan (KGZ)
- Laos (LAO)
- Latvia (LVA)
- Lebanon (LBN)
- Lesotho (LSO)
- Liberia (LBR)
- Libya (LBY)
- Liechtenstein (LIE)
- Lithuania (LTU)
- Luxembourg (LUX)
- Macau (MAC)
- Macedonia (MKD)
- Madagascar (MDG)
- Malawi (MWI)
- Malaysia (MYS)
- Maldives (MDV)
- Mali (MLI)
- Malta (MLT)
- Marshall Islands (MHL)
- Mauritania (MRT)
- Mauritius (MUS)
- Mexico (MEX)
- Micronesia, Federated States of (FSM)
- Moldova (MDA)
- Monaco (MCO)
- Mongolia (MNG)
- Montenegro (MNE)

- Morocco (MAR)
- Mozambique (MOZ)
- Namibia (NAM)
- Nepal (NPL)
- Netherlands (NLD)
- New Caledonia (NCL)
- New Zealand (NZL)
- Nicaragua (NIC)
- Nigeria (NGA)
- Niger (NER)
- Niue (NIU)
- Northern Mariana Islands (MNP)
- Norway (NOR)
- Oman (OMN)
- Pakistan (PAK)
- Palau (PLW)
- Panama (PAN)
- Papua New Guinea (PNG)
- Paraguay (PRY)
- Peru (PER)
- Philippines (PHL)
- Poland (POL)
- Portugal (PRT)
- Puerto Rico (PRI)
- Qatar (QAT)
- Romania (ROU)
- Russia (RUS)
- Rwanda (RWA)
- Saint Kitts and Nevis (KNA)
- Saint Lucia (LCA)
- Saint Martin (MAF)
- Saint Pierre and Miquelon (SPM)
- Saint Vincent and the Grenadines (VCT)
- Samoa (WSM)
- San Marino (SMR)

- Sao Tome and Principe (STP)
- Saudi Arabia (SAU)
- Senegal (SEN)
- Serbia (SRB)
- Seychelles (SYC)
- Sierra Leone (SLE)
- Singapore (SGP)
- Sint Maarten (SXM)
- Slovakia (SVK)
- Slovenia (SVN)
- Solomon Islands (SLB)
- Somalia (SOM)
- South Africa (ZAF)
- South Sudan (SSD)
- Spain (ESP)
- Sri Lanka (LKA)
- Sudan (SDN)
- Suriname (SUR)
- Swaziland (SWZ)
- Sweden (SWE)
- Switzerland (CHE)
- Syria (SYR)
- Taiwan (TWN)
- Tajikistan (TJK)
- Tanzania (TZA)
- Thailand (THA)
- Timor-Leste (TLS)
- Togo (TGO)
- Tonga (TON)
- Trinidad and Tobago (TTO)
- Tunisia (TUN)
- Turkey (TUR)
- Turkmenistan (TKM)
- Tuvalu (TUV)
- Uganda (UGA)

- Ukraine (UKR)
- United Arab Emirates (ARE)
- United Kingdom (GBR)
- United States (USA)
- Uruguay (URY)
- Uzbekistan (UZB)
- Vanuatu (VUT)
- Venezuela (VEN)
- Vietnam (VNM)
- Virgin Islands (VGB)
- West Bank (WBG)
- Yemen (YEM)
- Zambia (ZMB)
- Zimbabwe (ZWE)

5. Q5: When submitting a bug report, did you refer to the bug report template in the project? *

请仅选择一个答案。

- Yes 跳至第 6 题
- No 跳至第 14 题

submit the report

6. Q6. How important guidelines are to the GitHub *

(Mark only one option)

请仅选择一个答案。

- Unwise (e.g., It will harm my or my team's productivity)
- Unimportant (e.g., I will not use it)
- Neutral
- Worthwhile (e.g., I will use it help software development)
- Essential (e.g., I will use it every day to help software development)
- I do not know
- 其他: _____

7. Q7. Do you agree that projects with different popularity (star numbers) have different needs for templates? *

(Mark only one option)

请仅选择一个答案。

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Not necessarily
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

8. Q8. Do you agree that different types of projects (e.g., database, library, framework, plugin, toolkit, platform, etc.) have different needs for templates? *

(Mark only one option)

请仅选择一个答案。

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Not necessarily
- Agree
- Strongly Agree

9. Q9: When filling out a bug report, if the project provides a report template, do you agree this can help you write more detailed and accurate bugs? *

(Mark only one option)

请仅选择一个答案。

- Strongly disagree
- Disagree
- Not necessarily
- Agree
- Strongly agree

10. Q10: Why did you refer to the report? *

(Mark only one option per row)

请在每行中仅选择一个答案。

	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Neutral	Agree	Strongly Agree	I don't know
It can reduce the number of duplicated issues	<input type="radio"/>					
It can reduce the number of issues with missing elements	<input type="radio"/>					
It can reduce the number of the issues discussed	<input type="radio"/>					
It can increase the number of the issues fixed	<input type="radio"/>					

11. Q11: How important is each of the following factors to the quality of your bug report template? *

(Mark only one option per row)

请在每行中仅选择一个答案。

	Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely	I don't know
Correctness (e.g., spell correctly)	<input type="radio"/>					
Completeness (e.g., have complete descriptive information)	<input type="radio"/>					
Up-to-Dateness (e.g., latest version information)	<input type="radio"/>					
Internationalization (e.g., have templates in multiple languages)	<input type="radio"/>					
Usability (e.g., consistent content format)	<input type="radio"/>					
Readability (e.g., explanatory description with fields)	<input type="radio"/>					

12. Q12: How important is each of the following guidelines for filling out a bug report? *

(Mark only one option per row)

请在每行中仅选择一个答案。

	Not at all	Slightly	Moderately	Very	Extremely	I don't know
No spelling mistakes	<input type="radio"/>					
Have multiple templates based on the different intention	<input type="radio"/>					
Have the essential field	<input type="radio"/>					
Have the required limitation of some essential fields	<input type="radio"/>					
The version field is updated in time	<input type="radio"/>					
Have multiple language bug report templates	<input type="radio"/>					
Adopt the structured bug report templates	<input type="radio"/>					
Fix the position of fields	<input type="radio"/>					
Have the link, such as the chat room link and contributing guidelines' link	<input type="radio"/>					
The irrelevant fields will be deleted in time	<input type="radio"/>					
Have the description of the field	<input type="radio"/>					

Have the emojis

13. Apart the above conclusions, do you have other ideas/considerations/concerns about bug report guideline? Please let us know!

do not submit the bug report

14. Q6: What's the reason you did not adopt the template to fill out the report?

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